

INTERFACES IN METAL AND INTERMETALLIC-CERAMIC COMPOSITES*

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ABSTRACT

A noticeable segregation of Si at the TiB_2/NiAl interface, the source of which is the Si in the Al that is used to process the composites, lowers the tendency to form a coherent interface. The $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{NiAl}$ interface, on the other hand, shows a strong tendency to form a semicoherent interface and this is facilitated by the lack of any segregation. The SiC/Al interface can be affected through the processing methods used since these might cause the possible anomalous penetration of Al into SiC. The controlling factors are the size and morphology of the SiC, the amount of ball milling the SiC was subjected to, and the possibility of contact with molten Al since this will form serrated interfaces due to a dissolution reaction.

Keywords: dissolution, crystallographic, semicoherent, bonding, SiC/Al , TiB_2/NiAl , $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{NiAl}$.

1. INTRODUCTION

The interest metal matrix composites have generated in the past is due to a number of unique properties or possible uses that these new materials possess or are capable of. A case in point is the SiC/Al composite prepared by powder metallurgy and the TiB_2/NiAl composite produced by the XDTM process. The increased strengthening observed is due to the strength of the bonding at the interface between the matrix and the reinforcement. A bond of some kind is then required in order to obtain the maximum strengthening. A sufficient bond is possible only when good wetting of the reinforcement by the matrix is obtained, and this is very much dependent on the surface properties of the ceramic reinforcement and the matrix. These properties are major variables in the success of different fabrication methods used to produce composites with the particular interface strength which will also lead to the best combination of yield strength, fracture toughness and ductility. Processing methods, such as powder metallurgy and liquid infiltration, are techniques wherein the fabrication temperature is such that the ceramic reinforcement is usually in contact with a liquid metal matrix. The presence of a liquid matrix will have an effect, not only on the ability of the matrix to more readily wet the reinforcement, but also on the chemical stability of the interface [1].

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In the past, four different models have been proposed to explain the type of bonding that exists at the interface between Al and SiC; these are: 1. The presence of a SiO₂ film at the interface to which both, the matrix and the reinforcement, adhere to; 2. Direct electronic bonding among the atoms across the interface; 3. a chemical bond due to a reaction at the interface that forms another compound, such as Al₄C₃; and 4. Diffusion bonding, although the best available data shows very little penetration even at temperatures close to 2000°C [2,3]. This last model was not expected, but was proposed as an explanation to some experimental results obtained by Arsenault and Pande [4].

The TiB₂/NiAl composite is a system where excellent bonding between the matrix and the reinforcement is achieved by the XDTM process [5]. During the XDTM process, the TiB₂ particles are formed in situ in the molten metal matrix, so they have clean, nonoxidized interfaces and typically are single crystals of high purity. Usually, the crystal structures of the metal matrix and the ceramic particles are so different that no simple topotaxial relationship exists in XDTM processed metal matrix composites [5]. The intriguing observation concerning the TiB₂/NiAl composites is the lack of dislocation generation due to cooling from high temperature (1400°C) annealing [6,7]. The predicted thermal residual stress should be very large and this stress should be relieved by dislocation generation. It is possible that an interface layer exists between the TiB₂ and the NiAl which can act as a stress absorber [8].

The purpose of the present investigation was two-fold. The first concerned itself with the TiB₂/NiAl. In this case it was required to determine the thickness of the interfacial layer, if such a layer exists; and to see if any consistent crystallographic relationship could be found between the matrix and the reinforcement. The second part dealt with the SiC/Al composite. It was necessary to determine whether or not diffusion of Al into SiC occurs, and if it does, then, to determine the conditions under which it does occur.

2. EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

Aluminum does not form any silicides, but it is known to form a number of other intermetallic compounds at the temperatures that are used in the fabrication of these composites. In order to avoid these complications and to prevent any artifacts this may have on the interface, it was decided to use an 1100 aluminum powder as the matrix with particulates of α-SiC as the reinforcement. The composite was prepared by mixing the components into a slurry by the use of a ball mill and then compacting the powder mixture at 650°C for about 1 hour. Once the composite had been prepared, a number of annealing treatments were carried out. Two different annealing procedures were chosen. One was set at 590°C for 500 hours in order to anneal the composite under a more chemically stable condition. The other was set at 680°C in order to consider the effect that the presence of a liquid matrix would have on the interface stability. Two different times, of 2 and 10 hours respectively, were used for the 680°C treatment. These samples were allowed to cool down in the furnace and were then removed, after which some of the samples were then given an additional anneal of 500 hours at 590°C. A sample was also prepared from the "as made" condition, that is, before either of the annealing treatments were carried out. This sample was used as the reference state which samples from the annealed treatments were compared to. TEM sample preparation and examination procedure are discussed elsewhere [4].

Composites of TiB₂/NiAl containing 0, 10 and 20 V% reinforcement were purchased from the Martin Marietta Co. Foils for conventional TEM were prepared by twin jet electrolytic polishing in a 5% perchloric acid-ethanol solution, whereas samples for high resolution electron microscopy (HREM) and X-ray energy dispersive spectroscopy (EDS) were prepared in the same way as for conventional TEM except they were ion milled from 10 minute to 1 hour to clean the

surface as the final procedure. Most of the conventional TEM work was carried out on the high voltage electron microscope (HVEM) with the operating voltage of one million volts at the Argonne National Laboratory. HREM and EDS analyses were performed on a JEOL 2000 FX-II analytical electron microscope.

3. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Despite the difference in their crystal structures and their random crystallographic orientation relationships, there are some interesting aspects of interfaces between $\alpha\text{-Al}_2\text{O}_3$ and NiAl. In some cases, it seems that one or two disordered atomic layers on the $\alpha\text{-Al}_2\text{O}_3$ side exist, as shown in Fig. 1. It is possible that this observation is an image effect.

In the case of the lower indexed planes of $\alpha\text{-Al}_2\text{O}_3$ aligned with that of the matrix, semicoherent interfaces were observed. For instance, Fig.2 shows a semicoherent interface where the {100} planes of NiAl aligned with {110} planes (in a rhombohedral coordinate system) of $\alpha\text{-Al}_2\text{O}_3$. By using a hard sphere model of the interfaces structure, the distance between misfit dislocations is $D = d_1d_2/(d_1 - d_2)$ [9], where d_1 and d_2 are the interplanar distances for reinforcements and the matrix, respectively. The interplanar distances of (100) plane in NiAl and (110) plane in $\alpha\text{-Al}_2\text{O}_3$ are 0.288 and 0.3479 nm, respectively. Calculated, $D = 1.673$ nm, which is just about six times as large as the interplanar distance of (100) planes in NiAl. In Fig. 2, six of the (100) planes in NiAl planes aligned with five of the (110) planes in $\alpha\text{-Al}_2\text{O}_3$ planes with one misfit dislocation on the matrix side. This agrees with the calculated value very well.

Coherent or semicoherent interface between TiB_2 and NiAl were not observed via HREM. At the $\text{TiB}_2\text{-NiAl}$ interface, there exists a very thin layer (maybe a different crystal structure, but too thin to obtain a microdiffraction pattern) of atoms which had a different lattice spacing, as shown in Fig. 3. The thickness of this layer was about 0.6 nm when the observation was made along the basal plane of TiB_2 .

The results discussed above indicate that the interface layer at the $\text{TiB}_2\text{-NiAl}$ interface is very thin (0.6 nm), therefore, it is not thick enough to absorb the thermal residual stress, but there is a possibility that the thermal residual stress is relaxed by diffusion of atoms which have a larger atomic radius than the matrix atoms in the interface region. This relaxation would occur because the matrix is in hydrostatic tension [8] and the oversized atoms would reduce the stress.

The possibility of segregation was investigated by X-ray EDS analysis. It is obvious from a consideration of the data that an interface layer does not exist at the $\alpha\text{-Al}_2\text{O}_3\text{-NiAl}$ interface. However, there was a Si segregation layer at the $\text{TiB}_2\text{-NiAl}$ interface, but is too thin to act as a shock absorber of the thermal residual stress.

In the SiC/Al composite, there was no observable difference between the samples observed in the "as made" condition and those annealed at 590°C, irrespective of the annealing time (in some cases up to about 1000 hours). The processing temperature was carefully monitored so that at no time did it increase beyond 650°C. Fig.4 shows the hexagonal structure of the SiC. The interface was seen to be rather flat and clean, devoid of any segregation or any substantial interfacial reaction, as can be seen in Fig.4. We can conclude from the X-ray linescan data that there is no diffusion of Al into SiC at temperatures below 650°C; this being the case, irrelevant of what the annealing time, is in agreement with the previous conclusions arrived at by Cao et.al. [3].

Figure 1. HREM micrograph of α - Al_2O_3 -NiAl interface. Arrows indicate the disturbed interface.

Figure 2. HREM micrograph of α - Al_2O_3 -NiAl interface. Arrows indicate the misfit dislocations in the NiAl.

Figure 3. HREM micrograph of TiB_2 - NiAl interface. Arrows indicate the silicon segregated layer.

Figure 4. Interface of sample of SiC - Al annealed for 500 hours at 590°C . The small circles are locations of X-ray analysis.

This is not the case with samples that were in contact with liquid Al. These samples showed two types of interfaces; some were similar to those observed at 590°C (i.e. they exhibited no diffusion or any interfacial reactions) and others which showed that an extensive interfacial reaction had occurred, as can be seen from Fig. 5. No statistical counting procedure was carried out in order to obtain the volume percent of these particles as a function of the total SiC population; but it should be pointed out that these particles are not difficult to find in the observed areas so we can deduce that this is not just a simple occurrence on some selected particles but a more general effect throughout the sample. These samples showed the appearance of interfaces with an extensive serrated or jagged profile. Linescan profiles, taken from these interfaces showed a substantial penetration of Al into the SiC, up to about 100 nm; in fact, about 25 % Al is seen to be present within 25 nm from the interface. These concentrations are too large to have been produced by fluorescence of Al due to Si X-rays, while the absorption effect is considered to be small since very thin regions were used for all of the X-ray analyses. The drop in the Al concentration at the interface is probably an ion milling artefact since Al is removed at a faster rate than Si, especially in high stress regions (such as an interface). The bright field image, as shown on Fig. 6, show how substantial amounts of Al have penetrated in between some of the dissolving planes of the SiC. As the SiC dissolves, the Al "penetrates in" through these channels that open up (as shown by the arrow) and X-ray analyses taken from this region showed the Al concentration to be as high as 50 % of the total count. We can then conclude that a substantial amount of Al has penetrated into the SiC when the Al is present at the interface in liquid form. The interface appearance and concurrent linescans did not change for the samples annealed at 680°C for 2 hours as compared with those that had been annealed at the same temperature for 10 hours; so that the interfacial reaction seems to occur rather fast and to reach a saturation point within the first 2 hours. Also, linescan profiles taken from samples which had been given an additional annealing at 590°C, after being in contact with liquid Al, showed no additional change in the concentration profiles or in the interfacial appearance.

4. CONCLUSIONS

From data obtained, it is possible arrive at the following conclusions:

1. The Al-SiC interface is chemically stable at temperatures below 650°C and this prevents the diffusion of Al into SiC at these temperatures.
2. There is a substantial dissolution of SiC in the presence of a liquid Al matrix.
3. There is a significant penetration of Al into SiC at temperatures above 650°C.
4. The dissolution of SiC proceeds along the basal planes; it occurs very fast until a saturation point is reached.
5. In the XDTM processed TiB₂/NiAl composites, NiAl formed an excellent bond with the reinforcement TiB₂ particles, as well as the α -Al₂O₃.
6. No consistent crystallographic orientation relationships have been found between the NiAl matrix and TiB₂ or α -Al₂O₃ particles, although in some cases, one or two low indexed crystallographic planes of TiB₂ or α -Al₂O₃ might be aligned with those of NiAl.
7. Silicon segregation has been found in the TiB₂-NiAl interface region. No coherent or semicoherent interfaces have been observed between the TiB₂ and the NiAl, and the Si layer is too thin to absorb any of the thermal residual stress.
8. There is a strong tendency for the formation of semicoherent interfaces between α -Al₂O₃ and NiAl. No segregation has been found at these interfaces.

Figure 5. Interface of SiC in contact with liquid Al. The small circles are locations of X-ray analysis.

Figure 6. Bright field image of SiC-Al interface.

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